

NEW, UNUSUAL AND NONCLASSICAL BEHAVIOR
OF THIN-WALLED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Examples are discussed which illustrate several new, unusual and nonclassical effects that are present in thin-walled composite structures. Some of the unusual deformation characteristics occur naturally, such as the apparent increased flexibility of thin-walled beam structures due to bending-transverse shear and extension-transverse shear elastic couplings. Others are created intentionally, such as the exaggerated Poisson expansion in the tailored wing covers that produces elastic chordwise camber deformations.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Elastic Tailoring; Design.

1. INTRODUCTION

A significant attribute of laminated composites is their design flexibility. The layers or plies of a laminate are, in fact, modular units which can be selected to provide distinct material properties and fiber orientations. It is possible, therefore, to "tailor" the properties of

composites to meet specific design requirements. Engineers are learning to exploit this flexibility to produce unique structures tailored to the application. An outstanding example is the swept forward wing of the Grumman/AF/DARPA X-29 Fighter.

Elastic tailoring refers to the utilization of the design flexibility of composites to achieve performance goals. The goals are usually accomplished by selecting an appropriate structural concept, fiber orientation, ply stacking sequence and a blend of materials. Grid stiffened structural concepts are particularly useful for elastic tailoring of structures because stiffeners of unidirectional material can be oriented to create a wide variation of elastic properties. Examples of these structures appear in Figure 1.

In this paper, we review recent findings pertaining to new, unusual and nonclassical behavior of thin-walled beams of conventional laminated construction, extend consideration to thin-walled grid stiffened structures and present new findings pertaining to high aspect ratio wing concepts under development at University of California, Davis. A central feature of the wing designs is the use of continuous filament grid stiffened configurations for the wing box covers. This type of stiffening concept is very effective for creating exaggerated behavioral characteristics for tailoring purposes.

2. NEW ELASTIC COUPLINGS

2.1 Classical Coupling Mechanisms The pioneering work on thin-walled composite beams is by Mansfield and Sobey (1). It is based upon classical assumptions --- Bernoulli-Euler bending and Batho-Bredt torsion. The authors discuss the two classical elastic tailoring mechanisms of bending-twist coupling and extension-twist coupling and the means of fabricating thin-walled beams in order to produce them. Unfortunately, the classically based theory has been shown to be inadequate to accurately describe composite beam behavior (2,3). Two nonclassical effects, torsional warping and transverse shear response, are important and must be present in any general purpose analysis of composite beams.

Bending-twist coupling and extension-twist coupling have been used effectively for tailoring composite aircraft structures. The former has been applied to aeroelastic tailoring of lifting surfaces and the latter to rotor blades.

2.2 Two New Coupling Mechanisms Two new elastic coupling mechanisms that occur in thin-walled composite tubular beams, bending-transverse shear and extension-transverse shear, are presented and evaluated in Refs. 3 and 4. These new coupling mechanisms were not discovered earlier because classical-type theory, which ignores transverse shear effects, was utilized by Mansfield and Sobey (1). The nature and engineering consequences of these elastic couplings has been explored in Ref. 4 by studying two special limiting wall stiffness configurations which exhibit distinct, archetype responses.

2.3 Two Special Configurations Tailored response utilizing elastic coupling mechanisms for thin-walled tubular beams is achieved by skewing angle plies with respect to the beam axis. Two limiting archetype configurations are shown in Figs. 2 and 3. The circumferentially uniform stiffness (CUS) configuration produces extension-twist coupling with bending-transverse shear as a parasitic coupling mechanism. The other configuration, circumferentially asymmetric stiffness (CAS), produces bending-twist coupling with extension-transverse shear as a parasitic coupling mechanism. The angle θ in Figs. 2 and 3 denotes the dominant angle ply orientation in the upper and lower surface wall configurations.

2.4 Illustrative Applications The new coupling mechanisms have been investigated for circular cross section tubular beams with both CUS (Fig. 4) and CAS (Fig. 6) wall configurations (4). The graphite-epoxy wall construction corresponds appropriately to the upper and lower zones of the tubes shown in Figs. 2 and 3.

The results of bending a CUS tube with a uniformly distributed loading (Fig. 4) appear in Fig. 5. Four predictions based upon the classical Bernoulli-Euler (BE) type of theory and three shear deformation theories are presented. The theory SD3 is the complete theory of Ref. 2 which has been thoroughly validated. It is seen that the actual deflections (SD3) are approximately twice the classical predictions (BE). An analysis of these results indicates that bending-transverse shear coupling is the major cause of the beam appearing to be near twice as flexible as classical theory predicts. Details may be found in Ref. 4.

The results of stretching a CAS tube with distributed centrifugal loading (Fig. 6) appear in Fig. 7. The prediction of classical theory (CL) is very stiff compared to the complete beam theory (CBT) of Ref. 2. The difference is due entirely to extensive-transverse shear coupling.

2.5 Conclusion These findings indicate that with designed-in elastic couplings there are unwanted parasitic couplings present. These parasitic couplings cause the structures to respond as if they are much more flexible for certain modes of deformation. The magnitude of the effects produced are enormous, and it is evident that modeling and analysis methodology must account correctly for these nonclassical influences.

3. ELASTICALLY TAILORED WING DESIGNS

3.1 Wings With Elastically Produced Chordwise Camber It has become accepted practice to consider tailoring of wing bending and twisting deformations. At UC Davis a new step has been taken --- tailoring of chordwise deformations.

Structural tailoring concepts have been developed to create wings with elastically produced camber for the purpose of increasing the lift generated by the wing. The usual means of accomplishing this in use today is with controls, the most common of which are flaps. If natural, intrinsic means are used to enhance lift, flap requirements and their associated

systems may be reduced, thereby achieving increased simplicity, reliability and weight savings. The fundamental mechanisms that are utilized produce camber deformations in response to the usual loading of the wing such as bending moments and torque. The camber enhances the production of lift and further modifies the loads. Significant lift increases may be produced by using modern composite material systems.

A Record of Invention has been filed with the University of California Patent, Trademark and Copyright Office pertaining to the camber-producing structural concepts. It is designated UC Case No. 90-116-1 and is entitled "Wings With Elastically Produced Camber." The desired effects are depicted in Fig. 8.

3.2 Wing Cover Design Application For one high-aspect-ratio wing camber producing concept, a large effective Poisson's ratio is desired for the wing covers. This can be accomplished by utilizing a stiffener pattern and a balanced skin layup as shown in Fig. 9a. The spanwise coordinate is denoted by x and the chordwise coordinate by y . The in-plane stress resultants for the wing cover are

$$N_{xx} = A_{11}\epsilon_{xx} + A_{22}\epsilon_{yy} \quad (1)$$

$$N_{yy} = A_{12}\epsilon_{xx} + A_{22}\epsilon_{yy} \quad (2)$$

$$N_{xy} = A_{66}\gamma_{xy} \quad (3)$$

where ϵ_{xx} , ϵ_{yy} , and γ_{xy} are the membrane strains and A_{11} , A_{12} , A_{22} , and A_{66} are membrane stiffnesses.

If the stiffnesses of the stiffeners are accounted for in an averaged manner, the A_{ij} 's will be the "smeared" stiffnesses over the area of the panel. These are given by

$$A_{ij} = A_{ij}^0 + A_{ij}^1 \quad (4)$$

The superscripts "0" and "1" refer to the skin and stiffener stiffnesses, respectively. For the laminated composite skin, these stiffnesses are obtained using classical lamination theory. For the stiffeners modeled as one-dimensional elements, the membrane stiffnesses are given by

$$\begin{aligned} A_{11}^1 &= 2 h n E_{11}^1 \cos^4\theta_1 \\ A_{12}^1 &= 2 h n E_{11}^1 \sin^2\theta_1 \cos^2\theta_1 \\ A_{22}^1 &= 2 h n E_{11}^1 \sin^4\theta_1 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where E_{11}^1 is the extensional modulus of the stiffeners, h is the skin thickness, n is a stiffening parameter, and θ_1 is the inclination of the stiffener to the x -direction. The stiffening parameter n is defined as

$$n = A_1 / p_1 h \quad (6)$$

where A_1 is the cross sectional area of an individual stiffener and p_1 is the distance between stiffeners.

by virtue of high-aspect-ratio wing geometry, the chordwise stress resultant N_{yy} is small and will be ignored. Therefore, Equations (1) and (2) are reduced to the form

$$\epsilon_{yy} = - (A_{12}/A_{22})\epsilon_{xx} \quad (7)$$

$$N_{xx} = K_{11}\epsilon_{xx} \quad (8)$$

where

$$K_{11} = A_{11} - A_{12}^2/A_{22} \quad (9)$$

K_{11} is the effective extensional membrane stiffness and A_{12}/A_{22} is the effective Poisson's ratio which may be related to the camber. The camber curvature κ_{yy} is given by

$$\kappa_{yy} = A_{12}/A_{22} \kappa_{xx} \quad (10)$$

where κ_{xx} is the spanwise curvature.

3.3 Sample Results and Discussion

The ability of the structural concept to enhance the effective Poisson's ratio is illustrated below. Material properties utilized in this study are given in Table 1. A preliminary study of the effects of skin fiber orientation for balanced angle plies on the effective Poisson's ratio is shown in Figure 9a. These results indicate that a skin orientation angle θ_o of 26° is optimum for the material system selected. Only $\pm\theta$ skin fiber orientations are considered in this illustration. In general, 0° and 90° plies may be added without altering the Poisson's ratio significantly. The addition of 0° plies produces designs that are structurally more efficient since the dominant load component is in the spanwise direction of the wing.

The influence of adding stiffeners to the skin on the effective Poisson's ratio is illustrated in Figure 9b. These results are for a skin orientation angle of 26° and four different values of the stiffening parameter n (see Equation 6). The values for n equal to 0.0, 0.5, 1.0, and 1.5 correspond to the no stiffening, light stiffening, medium stiffening, and heavy stiffening cases, respectively. For a heavily stiffened panel ($n=1.5$), the value for the effective Poisson's ratio is about 2.8. These results illustrate the effectiveness of utilizing grid-stiffened structural concepts in elastic tailoring applications.

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

With the examples that have been discussed, we have illustrated several of the new, unusual and nonclassical effects that are present in thin-walled composite structures. Some of the

unusual deformation characteristics occur naturally, such as the apparent increased flexibility of thin-walled beam structures due to bending-transverse shear and extension-transverse shear elastic couplings. Others are created intentionally, such as the exaggerated Poisson expansion in the tailored wing covers that produces elastic chordwise camber deformations.

It is essential to be aware of these effects when modeling and analyzing or experimentally evaluating composite structural configurations. Experience gained with conventional structures made of isotropic materials may be a poor guide for successfully treating geometrically similar composite structures.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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6. REFERENCES

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TABLE 1 NOMINAL MECHANICAL PROPERTIES FOR AS4/3501-6
GRAPHITE-EPOXY UNIDIRECTIONAL MATERIAL

LONGITUDINAL MODULUS	137.89 GPa	(20.00 Msi)
TRANSVERSE MODULUS	11.31 GPa	(1.64 Msi)
IN-PLANE SHEAR MODULUS	6.00 GPa	(0.87 Msi)
MAJOR POISSON'S RATIO	0.30	0.30

FIGURE 1. Grid Configurations

FIGURE 2. CUS construction

FIGURE 3. CAS construction

FIGURE 4. Bending of CUS beam

FIGURE 5. CUS bending deflection

FIGURE 6. Stretching of CAS beam

FIGURE 7. CAS extension

FIGURE 8. Mechanisms to enhance lift

FIGURE 9. Effect of skin fiber and stiffener orientation on effective Poisson's ratio

